

The Effect of Raw Diet on Psoriasis

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Abstract:- Psoriasis is an Autoimmune Inflammatory skin disease. It is characterized by silvery scaly patches with Auspitz's sign. The modern lifestyle, stress, and wrong food habits are the aggravating factors of Psoriasis. Nutritious foods will help to improve immunity in Autoimmune disorders. The raw diet is packed with all the nutrients. In this study, Raw Diet is applied to managing psoriasis. The raw fruits and vegetables are given in the form of juices and salads. This study is done at Sree Rama Krishan Medical College hospital of Naturopathy and Yogic Sciences, Kulasekharam. The samples of 30 patients between the age of 25-60years, for 6 months. The patients are categorized as Group A – 10 psoriasis patients, Group B – 10 other skin disease patients, and Group C- 10 healthy persons as a control group. Nutrients and Phyto-nutrients present in raw vegetables and fruits help to reduce the inflammation and severity of the psoriasis Group A Psoriasis got the result of 98% relief from the symptoms and Group B results of 95% relief and Group C members results in improvement of their physical health.

Keywords:- Psoriasis, Autoimmune, Raw Diet, Nutrients, Fruits, Vegetables, Nuts.

I. INTRODUCTIONS

Psoriasis is the most prevalent Autoimmune Inflammatory skin disease. The current study tells that about 125 million people's affected worldwide. According to world psoriasis day studies shows that 2-3% of the total population have psoriasis. In India about 0.44-2.8% of the population have psoriasis. It is characterized by silvery scaly patches with Auspitz's sign on the elbows, knees, scalp, hands, and legs. Symptoms like itching, stinging, and pain over the skin. The modern lifestyle, stress, and wrong food habits are the aggravating factors of Psoriasis. If a person is not taking the proper Nutritious foods that may cause immunodeficiency. This creates significant impairments in our cell-mediated immunity, phagocyte function, complement system, secretory Ig A antibody concentration, and cytokine production. Nutrients like protein, Omega 3 fatty acids, vitamins like A, D, E, C, B6, and B9, Minerals like Iron, Copper, Zinc, Selenium, and other substances like Phyto-nutrients, Probiotics, Anti-oxidants, Anti-inflammatory rich foods have the significant role in our immunity in Auto-immune

disorders. For this study Raw vegetables, fruits and nuts are chosen for treating Psoriasis.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

➤ Materials

Raw Vegetables, Fruits, Nuts.

➤ Methods

This is an experimental study that includes 30 patients between the age of 25-60years, for 6 months. The patients are categorized as Group A – 10 psoriasis patients, Group B – 10 other skin disease patients, and Group C- 10 healthy persons as a control group. Psoriasis is graded as Mild (Affects less than 3% of the body) Moderate (Affects 3-10% of the body) Severe (Affects more than 10% of the body).

Parameters used in this study are regular symptomatic changes recorded skin thickness and Auspitz's sign. For diagnosis, a skin biopsy is done. This study is done at Sree Rama Krishan Medical College hospital of Naturopathy and Yogic Sciences, Kulasekharam. The patients are hospitalized for 21days and the remaining days are advised to follow the Raw diet chart and regular weekly checkups are done.

Table 1.1

SEVERITY	GROUP A	GROUP B	GROUP C
MILD	6	5	-
MODERATE	3	4	-
SEVERE	1	1	-

Table 1.1: shows the severity of the patient

Table 1.2

DAYS	6 am	8.30 am	11.30 am	1 pm	3 pm	5.30 pm	7 pm
Day 1 to Day 21	Tender coconut water	Fruits and Nuts (Apple, orange, musk melon, watermelon, Guava, papaya, Banana)	Amla juice	Raw vegetable salad (Carrot, Cucumber, Tomato, Beetroot, cabbage, coriander leaves, mint leaves)	Carrot juice	Fruits (Apple, orange, musk melon, watermelon, Guava, papaya, Banana)	Apple juice

Table 1.2: shows the given diet (1 to 21 days)

Table 1.3

DAYS	6 am	8.30 am	11.30 am	1 pm	3 pm	5.30 pm	7 pm
Day 22 to Day 90 (Follow up)	Tender coconut water	Fruits (Apple, orange, musk melon, watermelon, Guava, papaya, Banana)	Nuts and Dry fruits (Almond, walnut, cashew nut, peanut, Dates, Raisins)	Vegetables (Carrot, Cucumber, Tomato, Beetroot, cabbage, coriander leaves, mint leaves)	AmlaJuice/ Carrot Juice	Fruits (Apple, orange, musk melon, watermelon, Guava, papaya, Banana)	Apple Juice/ Lime Juice

Table 1.3: shows the given diet (22 to 90 days)

III. DISCUSSION

For this study, particular fruits, vegetables, dry fruits, and nuts were given in raw form. Tender coconut, Dates, Raisins, Almond, Walnut, Cashew, Peanut, Amla, Apple, Muskmelon, Watermelon, Orange, Lime, Guava, Papaya, Banana, Carrot, Cucumber, Tomato, Beetroot, cabbage, coriander leaves, mint leaves were added in their diet. They are rich in immune-enhancing nutrients like Protein, Vitamin-A, E, C, B6, and B9, Iron, Zinc, Selenium, Copper, Probiotics, Omega 3 Fatty Acids, Phytochemicals like Beta-Carotene, and Flavonoids are rich in this diet. They have Anti-inflammatory, and Anti-oxidants properties that promote the healing of Psoriasis. Protein helps to form immunoglobulin and antibodies to fight against infection. Omega 3 Fatty acids reduce inflammation and improve the function of B-cells and WBC. Vitamin A (Beta Carotene) helps in the activation and proliferation of Lymphocytes and also has an Anti-inflammatory effect.

Vitamin E acts as an Anti-oxidants and helps to protect cells from damage caused by free radicals. Vitamin E helps develop, function, and regulate dendritic cells, macrophages, Natural killer cells, and immune cells. Vitamin C has an Anti-oxidants property which promotes wound healing. Vitamin C helps in the proliferation of immune cells. Vitamin C protects the cell from oxidative stress. Vitamin C promotes phagocyte function and clears the infection site. B6(Pyridoxine) has Anti-oxidants and Anti-inflammatory properties that help in the healing of Psoriasis. B6 increases the production of antibodies and fights against infective agents. B9(Folate) regulates the immune responses. B9 enhances the proliferation of Lymphocytes and Natural killer cells activity. Iron is necessary for immune cell proliferation, activation, and maturation. Zinc helps in the development of WBC and induces cell-mediated immunity. Zinc promotes wound

healing, regulates immune functions, and acts as a co-factor for numerous antioxidant enzymes. Zinc is necessary for protein synthesis and in the process of collagen formation. Selenium has the properties like anti-inflammatory and anti-oxidants that will improve immunity by reducing oxidative stress and inflammation. Copper can generate superoxide ions and kills microorganism. Probiotics promote the activity of T-cells and Natural killer cells. Probiotics boost the level of immune cells in mucous members. Flavonoids act as an anti-inflammatory and anti-oxidant effect helping to enhance immunity and promote healing. Thus foods have a major role in the healing process of psoriasis.

IV. RESULT

This study shows that the effect of Group A results in 98% relief from the symptoms and Group B results in 95% relief and finally, Group C members results in improvement of their body health.

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